

Using Review Sentences in Teaching Grammar

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Abstract: Review sentences is type of grammar practicing which is the easiest way to checking how is the students' understanding about the previous grammar rules given, especially for college students. We are going to define some steps that we need to apply in review sentences. Moreover, it is still important to upgrading collage students' grammar understanding because English as EFL will getting hard when they are not really concern about the grammar. This paper will discuss the benefit of review sentences in checking students understanding in the certain type of grammar rules.

Keywords: *Review Sentences, grammar*

INTRODUCTION

Grammar is one problem of students in studying English in EFL. Some of them really care of grammar, but others really do not care about grammar. Only several students who are eagerly to find it in grammar books or other sources, but some of them get desperate with the grammar and give up to continue the sentences. As the lecture delivered the grammar rule to guide the students about grammar and he/she wish that

the students will aware about the grammar. But, unfortunately most of the students give up to continue the sentence because they cannot the rule of the grammar for that text.

The lecture should try other way in teaching to make them understand more grammar rules. In the other hand, lectures need to know well the level of the students' grammar understanding so he/she will not make mistake in categorizing the students' level. One of the most crucial things is how to exploring and checking their grammar understanding. Review sentences is one of the ways of checking students' understanding. We have to check, whether review sentences are able to describe students' grammar understanding.

Why Using Review Sentences for Teaching Grammar in College?

The importance of grammar is very clear. When we get some difficulties in understanding sentences' arrangement in a text it means that we need to improve our grammar understanding. So, the other basic thing that we should master in studying language is its grammar rules. We have to know the grammar to help us in understanding the context and the sentences arrangement. It is also stated in Dibdyaningsih (2018) that grammar is an important in accomplish several types of test and it is important to distinguish time or event. So, grammar is important lesson in learning new language.

Today, students like to have computerized media during the class, otherwise they will have their own activity and ignore the lecture. So, lecture should find a nice media which can activate students to involve in the course well. An online media which can be applied in the grammar class is *review sentences*, it is an activity that can help lecture in knowing the students' grammar understanding. It also helps the lecture to checking the students' grammar level. Wright, Betteridge and Buckby (2005) stated that language learning is very difficult and efforts are required over a long period of time. Special attention is given to the problems related teaching and learning grammar.

The Advantages of Using Review Sentences for Teaching College

Based on the earlier explanation, we can conclude that grammar is one of good tools for students to understand the new language. It also refers to that when students cannot understand the grammar, they will get difficulties in understanding sentences. Sometimes, students know the word in meaning but they cannot understand the context because it is going in different meaning when it applied different grammar.

In addition, a review sentence is an innovating media which can make language learning enjoyable and trigger students to active in the class. Learners of new language have to deal with all grammar rules during their acquisition. In order to learn and practice new grammar rule, learners should participate in different task-based activities in their classroom there are many interactive games, memorizing rules and conversation exercise. Such activities also include grammar practice which especially focus on helping learners develop and apply grammar in different contexts by making the class fun.

Therefore, it is necessary to explore whether students learn grammar effectively through *review sentences* and how they learn it. Normally students memorize the rules of grammar in a list, and when they fail with this way, they will say that it is caused by their bad analysis. Research and publications have shown that this is not a very effective way to study. Wright, Betteridge and Buckby (2005) stated that language learning needed efforts and required over a long period of time. Special attention is given to the problems related teaching and learning grammar.

Moreover, Sadat (2017) said that lecture should blend grammar teaching with communicative language teaching in order to achieve the grammar understanding. How lecture apply any media to teach grammar will influence student's grammar understanding. It is because when they didn't interest with the teaching process, they will ignore the lecture and doing anything else, it will make them cannot understand what the lecture has explained. So, lecture should develop a creative and interactive media in teaching grammar.

Studying grammar can be used many different media. One of the learning media that is used in STKIP PGRI Bangkalan is 'review sentences' that seems have many benefits for those who are studying grammar. Thus, this study was conducted to identify how 'review sentences' may facilitate the teaching process and help students to study grammar. And it has tried to find out whether 'review sentences' can improve students' grammar understanding.

Using Review Sentences to Teach Grammar

It has been described previously, that review sentences have many advantages in teaching grammar. Moreover, the lectures can use it as alternatives way in teaching grammar. The lecture should try to have this activity in order to make the students interesting to upgrade their grammar and ability in understanding the grammar rules based on the context. Nowadays, there are so many books / e-books which are talking about a 'review sentences'. Some of them can be purchased in both conventional and online stores, while the online version can be subscribed. Furthermore, lectures are should be not worries about the material of review sentences that we can use freely in several website. Oxford's website (<https://elt.oup.com/student/livinggrammar/?cc=id&selLanguage=id>) is one of those which are free. In this website, we can do online many exercises of grammar.

Picture 1. Online grammar book with review sentences.

Hendra Sudarso, Haris Dibdyaningsih
Using Review Sentences in Teaching Grammar

Moreover, in this online book, we can have several types of review sentences. We also may develop some activities that can trigger student's grammar awareness. Here is some ideas of review sentences activities:

a. Dialogue

Picture 2. Online complete dialogue in elementary level.

Dialogue is one of sentence type which can be applied in review sentences. Students can fill the missing words based on the dialogue of the recording. Moreover, students can choose the topic based on their level. Furthermore, they answer and get the score directly after finish.

b. Match sentences

Picture 3. Online complete dialogue in intermediate level.

Match sentences is a type of review sentences, it helps students to join two part of sentences. In this online book, students can drag the sentence and they can do it individually or in group, lecture only need to check the final score. Furthermore, lecture can ask students to make their own sentence and ask other students or other group to match the sentences. This type of review sentences is very effective in trigger students for being active in the class.

c. Fill in the missing word

The most famous of reviewing sentences is ‘fill missing words’, this type of review sentences is also the easiest form that commonly used in grammar class. Lecture only need to take some sentences in the article and erase the word which suitable for the grammar rules that they have learnt. Moreover, for exploring students’ grammar understanding, lecture can ask the students to create some sentences based on the topic of grammar and they may exchange their sentences with other students or with other groups. Lecture can use this kind of activity as a quiz activity or grouping activity and gets the score directly after they finish the activity.

Picture 4. Online fill missing word in pre-intermediate level.

Hendra Sudarso, Haris Dibdyaningsih Using Review Sentences in Teaching Grammar

Furthermore, Oxford online book also substitutes the book with some resources that very useful for both students and lecturers. All of them are free and can be downloaded for checking students or lecturer's grammar understanding.

Picture 5. Online download sources upper-intermediate level.

CONCLUSION

The use of review sentences online for teaching grammar offers many of advantages. That is why it is recommended that lecturers try to apply of this way as their alternative's material in teaching grammar. They also may ask their students to choose and decide their own level of review sentences activities. The students are allowed to divine which activities are suitable for them in divining the grammar based on the context of the sentences.

Since review sentences are available not only online but offline, lecturers can also teach of how students can increase their grammar understanding from 'Oxford living grammar' in the online version. It also can help them in understanding new rules by such kind of interesting materials through interactive online books. When students are good in grammar understanding, it can be said that they have conquering the language.

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